

Project Title – Impact of Digital Banking in India: Recent Trends and Challenges

Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of
Master of Business Administration (MBA)

By

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Declaration

I, **Anamika Thakur**, hereby solemnly declare that the project report titled "**Impact of Digital Banking in India: Recent Trends and Challenges**" submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of **Master of Business Administration (MBA)** is my original work.

I further declare that:

- This project has been carried out by me during the academic year 2026 under the supervision of **Swati Bhatt**.
- The work has not been submitted previously to any other university, institution, or examination body for the award of any degree, diploma, or certification.
- All sources of information used in this report have been duly acknowledged and referenced in accordance with academic ethics and plagiarism norms.
- The data presented in this report is authentic to the best of my knowledge and has not been fabricated or manipulated.
- I understand that if any part of this declaration is found to be false, my project may be rejected and disciplinary action may be taken as per institutional rules.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Digital Banking in India is not a merely recent phenomenon or a sudden reaction to modern technology; rather, it represents the culmination of a long-term, decade-long process of structural transformation within the Indian Banking system. This evolution has seen the sector move away from traditional paper based 'brick and mortar' banking towards a seamless digital ecosystem

1.1 Background

The term bank has been either derived from Old Italian word "banca" or from a French word "Banque" both mean a Bench or money exchange table. In olden days, European money lenders or money changers used to display coins of different countries in big quantity on benches or tables for the purpose of lending or exchanging. The concept of modern banking was first traced in medieval Florence in 1397. A powerful merchant family named Medici established a network of shops that allowed patrons to place money on account and withdraw the money in another city that had a Medici representative. Many powerful families and even the Church kept their money in Medici banks. This allowed rich people to travel without the need to carry large sums of money and risk of robbery while travelling. Banking continued to gain popularity throughout Europe by 1700. Nearly every country in Europe had some form of established banking (Bhatt, V. 2020).

In India the banking era started in 1770 with the establishment of "Bank of Hindustan" by the British. "General Bank of India", "Bank of Bengal", "Bank of Bombay" and "Bank of Madras" was established thereon in 1786, 1809, 1840 and 1843 respectively as an independent unit and the later three were called Presidency Bank. These banks were later merged in 1920 to constitute Imperial Bank of India, which was later renamed to State Bank of India. It was nationalised on 1 January 1949. The first bank established by Indian people was Allahabad bank in 1865. A number of other banks such as Bank of India, Central Bank of India, Bank of Baroda, Canara Bank, Indian Bank, and Bank of Mysore were set up between 1906- 1913. The Reserve Bank of India was established on 1 April, 1935. The government of India passed the Banking Regulation Act, 1949 which provided RBI wide powers to supervise and become the apex institution in the banking and financial structure of the country. This phase is basically the First phase of Indian banking system.

The second phase of Indian banking system is recognised by nationalization of banks and the banking sector reforms, from 1969 to 1991. Indira Gandhi, the-then Prime Minister of India expressed the intention of the Government of India in the annual conference of the All India Congress Meeting in a paper entitled "Stray thoughts on Bank Nationalization" to nationalize the banks. The proposal of nationalization of bank was widely supported and thus on 19 July 1969 the government issued an ordinance to nationalize the 14 largest commercial banks of India. The ordinance received the presidential approval on 9 August, 1969. In 1980, 6 more commercial banks were nationalised. With the second step of nationalization, the government of India controlled around 91% of the banking business in India. Later on, in the year 1993, the government merged New Bank of India with Punjab National Bank. The merger resulted in the reduction of the number of nationalized banks from 20 to 19. The rate of growth of nationalized bank during the second phase was 4%. The reforms after 1991 were termed as third phase of Indian banking industry. In 1991, under the chairmanship of M. Narasimhan, a committee was set up, which worked for the liberalization of banking practices. The result of committee's efforts had huge impact on the changes in the banking practice. Quality services now become imbedded in the banking which was not prevailed during previous phases. With the emergence of phone banking and net banking, the entire system has become more convenient and swifter (Bhatt, V. 2020).

Structure of Commercial Banks in India

In order to fully understand the status quo of Indian banking industry and the challenges faced by it, the study analysed key indicators which include the market capitalisation of public and private sector banks, number of branches and ATMs across the country, credit deposit ratio, non-performing assets and its effect on the profitability of public sector banks. Indian banking industry has come a long way from the first phase with the largest public sector bank State Bank of India having a market capitalisation of 254708.41 billion Indian rupees and over 22414 branches across the country. HDFC is the largest private sector bank with a market capitalisation of 6687.26 billion Indian rupees and over 5314 branches across the country (Bhatt, V. 2020).

In respect of ATMs public sector bank outperformed the private sector in providing a large number of ATMs across the country whereas private sector banks had their ATMs presences limited to urban and metropolitan areas. Of the total ATMs provided by private sector bank 40% were located in metropolitan areas and 26.3% in urban areas. As compared to public sector banks 29.5% of the total ATMs of public sector bank were located in semi-urban areas, followed by 28.3% in urban areas, 21.8% in metropolitan areas and 20% in rural areas (Bhatt, V. 2020).

In order to improve the customer service, book keeping and MIS reporting, the need for computerization was felt in the Indian banking sector in late 1980s. Reserve Bank of India set up a Committee headed by Dr. C. Rangarajan on computerization in banks in 1988 (Harchekar, J. S. (2018).

1.2 Digital Banking in India

The banking industry is rapidly varying and diversifying its business operations as a result of a digital revolution. The subject of digital transformation in business activities in commercial banks is also getting a lot of attention from scholars, legislators, and businesses. Developing financial and banking software, digital banking, mobile banking solutions, fintech, etc., to be able to meet customer demand about interest rate liberalization, big data, mobile finance, risk management, internet finance, and customer relationship management are just a few examples of how commercial banks are undergoing a digital transformation (Indriasari et al., 2019).

Customers are no longer willing to queue in banks, or wait on the phone, for the basic banking services. They expect a facility to conduct their banking activities at any time and at any place. Irrespective of being a public sector or private sector bank, almost all of them have

given maximum significance to technological development and deployment. To illustrate, ATMs, plastic money (Credit Cards, Debit Cards and Smart Cards), online collection and payment services, online investments (Deposits and Mutual Funds), online De-mat and Trading accounts, Electronic Funds Transfer (ETF) and clearing services, branch networking, telephone banking, mobile applications and wallet, and internet banking are the outcomes of their initiative towards technological up gradation (Sharma, A., & Piplani, N. J. I. R. 2017).

India offers a distinct environment for the development of digital banking because of its sizable and diversified population. The goal of the nation's large-scale digital programs, such the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) and the Digital India campaign, is to use technology to empower millions of marginalized people and advance financial inclusion. Digital banking has emerged as a crucial facilitator of inclusive growth in this ever-changing environment, promising more accessibility to banking services, increased efficiency, and higher financial knowledge (Dhakane, M. R. M., & Lad, K. 2024). The introduction of digital banking in India has not only revolutionized the way banking services are delivered but also catalysed broader socioeconomic transformations.

This profound shift was not merely a result of technological progress, but rather the outcome of a deliberate and strategic policy framework designed to modernize the Indian financial landscape. To understand the depth of this impact, it is essential to examine the architecture that supports its revolution.

Core of this transformation is the incorporation of identity, connectivity, and availability, a combination that has affectively updated the relationship between the Indian citizen and the formal banking sector.

The Pillars of Digital Revolution: The JAM

A rapid growth of digital banking in India is anchored by a coordinated framework known as the **JAM**. This synergy of three distinct systems serves as the foundation for the 'Digital India' mission and is the primary tool behind the socio-economic milestones observed over the last decade.

- **J – Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY):** This started back in 2015 as a major step to bring banking to everyone in India. Before this, many people didn't even have a basic bank account. By opening over 500 million zero-balance accounts, the government shifted

the focus from serving only the wealthy to "mass banking," making it the first real step toward a digital economy for common people.

- **A – Aadhaar:** Aadhaar acts as the digital foundation for the whole system. Because it is a biometric ID, it made the "Know Your Customer" (e-KYC) process much faster and paperless. Instead of waiting days and submitting lots of documents, banks can now verify and sign up new customers almost immediately, which has really brought down the cost of running a bank.
- **M – Mobile Connectivity:** The mobile phone has basically become a "bank in our pocket". Because smartphones and data plans became so cheap in India that people no longer need to travel to a bank branch. Banking is now available 24/7, which is the most important part of the digital trend allowing anyone to send or receive money anytime and anywhere.

Core components of the Indian Digital banking Ecosystem

Building upon the Jam foundation, several key technological means have redefined the functional scope of commercial banks in India. Some of them are as follows

- **The UPI Boom:** If we look at the biggest change, it has to be UPI. It basically turned our mobile phones into a payment tool that works instantly. The coolest part about UPI is how it's used by everyone from a local street vendor selling vegetables to huge showrooms. UPI has made payments equal for everyone. It doesn't matter if you are a huge company or just a small street vendor, you don't need expensive machines anymore. All you need is a simple QR code printed on a piece of paper to start accepting digital payments from anyone.
- **Online Investments:** Digital banking isn't just for keeping money in a savings account anymore. Now, we have all-in-one platforms where you can handle mutual funds, ETFs, and stocks right from your phone. This has been a huge deal for people in Tier-2 and Tier-3 cities. In the past, investing felt like something only people in big cities like Mumbai or Delhi did, but now anyone with an internet connection can start a Demat account easily.
- **Direct Benefit Transfers (DBT):** One of the most useful things the government did was starting DBT i.e. Direct Benefit Transfers by linking Aadhaar directly to bank accounts, they can send subsidy money straight to the people who need it. This is a big deal for India because it cuts out the "middlemen" and stops money from getting

lost or stolen along the way. It makes the whole welfare system much more transparent and honest.

The widespread adoption of mobile banking, internet banking, digital payments, and other technology-driven financial services have democratized access to financial services, especially for marginalized and remote communities. However, alongside these opportunities, digital banking also presents various challenges, including cyber security risks, privacy concerns, and the digital divide (Dhakane, M. R. M., & Lad, K. 2024). A comprehensive understanding of the nuances within India's digital banking sector is essential for policymakers, regulators, and banking institutions to develop strategies that foster financial inclusion, stability, and innovation. Through a critical analysis of existing literature, this study aims to provide a deeper exploration of the opportunities and challenges inherent in nation's digital banking evolution.

1.3 Research Problem Statement

The rapid digital progress of the Indian banking sector accelerated by the "Digital India" mission and the Unified Payments Interface (UPI) revolution has successfully brought millions into the formal financial fold. However this unprecedented growth has raised a complex set of challenges that threaten the sustainability of the digital ecosystem.

The core of the problem lies in the **Digital Paradox** currently facing the Indian economy. On one hand, India leads the world in real-time digital transaction volumes; on the other hand a significant portion of the population remains digitally vulnerable. Despite the existence of over millions of Jan Dhan accounts, there is a persistent digital gap where rural and semi-urban users find it difficult with lack of digital literacy, understanding of banking applications and lack of network infrastructure.

Furthermore there is a rise in social engineering frauds, phishing, and unauthorized data breaches have created a pervasive "Trust Deficit" among consumers. This problem prevents the total transition to a cashless India and therefore many users still perceive physical cash as a safer alternative to digital wallets.

One major challenge for bank management today is finding a balance between technology and personal service. While Indian banking is rapidly adapting to digital banking we are

losing the traditional face to face connection. This shift often leaves elderly and non tech customers feeling separated.

So, the main thing I want to look at this research is how digital banking is actually changing things in India. Even though almost everyone is using online banking and apps now, there are still a lot of big challenges like security risks and the fact that many people don't know how to use these tools safely and properly.

1.4 Research Questions

The research questions which this project will focus on are as follows:

1. How the transition from the traditional banking to digital banking has impacted customers.
2. What are the main barriers and the challenges faced by financial industries in implementation of digital banking.

1.5 Research Objectives

The main objectives of this report are as follows:

1. To study the evolution of digital banking in India.
2. To determine the benefits and problems Indian banking industry is experiencing.
3. To provide more solutions for the better implementation of this digitalization across India.

1.6 Research Significance

The significance of this research explains about the fast evolving digital banking in India. This research is important for the banking sector to understand the strengths and weaknesses of digital banking. For policy makers it can help in creating better digital infrastructure and also for students it serves as valuable resource to understand the latest digital trends in India.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The Indian Banking Industry has seen a dramatic transformation in the last decade where transition from the traditional banking to digital banking has occurred. This literature review observes the different institutional reports, papers, findings from the different journals and industry analysis published mostly in the last decade. The adoption of digital banking in India gained significant momentum following the demonetization of 2016, which forced both financial institutions and consumers to adapt the digital payment systems. Digitalization in banking is also very helpful in financial inclusion, transparency, accuracy and in maintenance of data more effortlessly among the financial institutions, banking sector in India. Digitalization plays a pivotal role in the economic development of the nation also.

The growth and acceptance of UPI is the best example that how a program if it's simple to use, low transaction cost and have security can prove to be such a successful initiative. UPI has not only changed the way Indians transact but has also been a catalyst for improving financial inclusion and digitalization in the country. Additionally, the arrival of COVID-19 pandemic increased the adoption of digital financial transactions in many countries, including India, further highlighting the significance of digital payment systems in today's global economy. Despite of remarkable growth in the digital transactions in India a number of challenges like internet connectivity, cyber frauds, technological disruptions, language barriers, limited computer literacy etc. are noticeable threats to the growth of digital financial transactions in India and has the capacity to create discrepancies between the societies. These challenges require a coordinated effort from government bodies, financial institutions, technology providers, and users themselves.

This study aims to observe the digital trends in banking and evolution of Indian banking system. By understanding the trends and challenges identified by the different scholars this section will view the shift from basic traditional banking to current time of fintech, artificial intelligence and central bank digital currencies. The review is organized into the following themes which are evolution of digital banking, its impact on the financial inclusion, emerging trends and key challenges faced by Indian banking sector.

2.1 Evolution of Digital Banking in India:

The evolution that digital banking has seen from traditional banking to digital banking holds many catalysts and initiatives from the Indian government. Many papers have discussed the driving forces behind the digital banking evolution in India. Some of the important studies are in the following section.

2.1.1 Foundations of Financial Inclusion:

This paper reviews the financial inclusion in India with respect to PMJDY. Data is collected from the secondary and primary data like direct interaction from people, by questionnaires. Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojna (PMJDY) was a transformational decision taken by the Prime Minister of India on 28 August 2014. This scheme's target was to promote financial inclusion in every household by at least providing a single account in the Bank. 'Sab ka sath sab ka vikas' i.e. inclusive growth altogether was the theme on which it was based. In this scheme a zero balance account was provided to the household with RuPay debit card and along with an accidental insurance cover of Rs 1 lakh. By January 26, 2015 those who have opened the account over and above the Rs1 lakh accident, they will be given life insurance cover of Rs 30,000. Holders will also avail Rs 5,000 overdraft facility after opening the bank account for six months. The limitation related to this study is that it is limited to the northern states of the country majorly (Bijoy, K. 2017).

The aim of this paper was to study the success of PMJDY. The author has taken a follow up study survey, a type of longitudinal study. PMJDY main objective of this scheme was the financial inclusion of India as before that much rural uneducated population was devoid of access to the banking facilities in India. Hence from this scheme households will not only have the bank accounts but may enjoy the benefits of economic growth and various government schemes with their own indigenous RuPay card in hand. As explained earlier RuPay card with inbuilt Rs 1 lakh accidental insurance cover to Aadhar linked accounts will be provided. After the release of PMJDY scheme the reach of banking sectors covered almost 95% of India's household. By June 2016, 4, 52,151 such villages were provided the banking services. Accounts opened under PMJDY as of February 2018 in Public sector banks total of 25.15 crore in which rural comprise 13.47 and urban 11.68, for regional rural banks the data is 5.00 crore in which rural comprise 4.22 and urban 0.78 and for private banks 0.99 crore in which rural comprise 0.60 and urban 0.39 making it a total of 31.14 crore. The

comprehensive data for the study is mainly collected from the districts of Karnataka (Singh & Naik, 2018).

2.1.2 Demonetization as a Catalyst for Digital Adoption:

The author studies the impact of demonetization on E-transaction in India. The research is based on the secondary data exclusively. Demonetization was also a very bold move by the Indian Government to restrain the shadow economy in India. Demonetization was withdrawal circulation of 500 and 1000 rupee notes. Prime Minister of India Shri Narendra Modi announced demonetization of high currency notes of 500 and 1000 on 8th November 2016 with immediate effect. By the end of March, 2016 RBI reported total amount of currency in circulation was Rs.16, 415 billion of which 86.4% in the form of 500 and 1000 rupee notes. The major objective behind demonetization was to stop the flow of black money in the market in the form of anti-money laundering, fake currency circulation, anti-terrorism funding etc., considering the impact of demonetization in India as people who were relying on the paper money only forced to adapt the digital mode of transaction or we can say demonetization forced our nation to adapt to the digital payment modes. This resulted in the sudden leap of cashless payments. The limitation according to the author is the lack of digital literacy across the country (Kathial, K. 2018).

The author has tried to explain the impact of demonetization on digital payment transaction. The study describes various ways of digital payment transactions, each having differentiating feature. The content of the study is taken from the secondary data sources; comparative approach is taken by the author to explain various digital payment methods. Demonetization in the country on 8th November 2016 was really a turning point for the economy of the country. Digital payments have changed the way every individual lived post demonetization and as the country has seen a remarkable growth in the cashless economy. PayTm, Mobikwik, Oxigen, PhonePe and many other merchants mobile banking and wallet companies provided various offers and benefits for making cashless economy easy to use and available to every individual. So we can say that demonetization has acted as a driving force for the digital banking system in India. There are various digital banking services such as NEFT i.e. National Electronic Fund Transfer; it helps in the bank to bank transfer of funds. RTGS stands for Real Time Gross Settlement; real time settlement of funds is done in this. IMPS stand for Immediate Payment System; it is an instant interbank transfer service. UPI stands for Unified Payment Interface; it's an application based interface. UPI is very flexible

and is used to transfer or receive funds through application. Mobile transactions include application based transaction compatible for mobile these can be UPI or application provided by private payment services like PayTm, Mobikwik etc. Payment timings for UPI, IMPS, E-Wallets, Debit/Credit Cards are 24/7 while for NEFTs these are 23 half hourly settlements; 8 AM to 7 PM. Transaction time for UPI, IMPS, Debit/Credit Cards and E-Wallets is instant or within 30 min while for NEFT it is nearly 2 hours. The limitation according to the report is that government should create more awareness related to the digital platforms and should held more awareness camps as well (Manocha et al., 2019).

2.1.3 The Rise of UPI and the Payment Revolution:

This paper's main objective is to examine digital payment revolution in India and various factors which catalysed this transformation. The data used in the report is secondary data that is collected from articles, books, and research reports. The research is all about understanding how digital payments revolutionized India. Digital payment methods after demonetization took a leap. As introduction of UPI i.e. Unified Payments Interface by National Payment Corporation of India on 2016 changed the way Indians were doing digital transactions. First of all UPI was an indigenous system and it offered many services to consumers. UPI enables small merchant to use digital payment services without any PQS machine use. It operates through phone application only. As BHIM application launched by the Hon'ble Prime Minister of India, Narendra Modi on 30th December 2016 to bring in Financial Inclusion to the nation and a digitally empowered society. Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM) is a payment app that lets you make simple, easy and quick transactions using Unified Payments Interface (UPI). Through BHIM application consumers can make easy payments through scanning QR or using the UPI ID. UPI allows a customer to pay directly from a bank account to different merchants, both online and offline, without the hassle of typing credit card details, IFSC code, or net banking/wallet passwords. By this UPI kind of became the most advanced system of the world and its adoption in India was the fastest (Kolte et al., 2020).

This study conducts a rigorous comparison of UPI adoption metrics across rural and urban districts. This study adopts a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design. Demonetization as it acted as a catalyst for the digital revolution in India, which led to widely accepted UPI system in India. UPI emerged as a transformative payment solution in India after its launch by National Payment Corporation of India in 2016. Its mobile-first architecture offered an extraordinary level of handiness, security, and affordability, directly challenging the

dominance of cash payments in India. Because it's one click solution for digital payments it's accepted by consumers very fast and local vendors, merchants, for delivery agents it became the favourite tool for digital payments which has somehow boosted the financial inclusion in India as well. Rural population in India has shown interest in UPI more than any other digital payment method due to the ease of using it. This study identifies a triad of critical barriers moderating rural adoption: (1) persistent digital and financial illiteracy, (2) inadequate last-mile internet and power infrastructure, and (3) a deep-seated trust deficit in digital transaction systems (Malik et al., 2025).

2.1.4 Fintech Integration and Modern Banking:

The paper explores the evolution of fintech in India and how it is transforming traditional banking. This Research paper follows a conceptual research design and relies solely on secondary data. Sources used from academic journal articles, RBI and government reports, NPCI and industry publications, and credible online resources related to fintech, digital payments, financial inclusion, and regulatory developments in India. Indian Financial sector has observed tremendous growth in last 20 years of time span as it has evolved from a traditional banking system to a digital banking sector. The advent of mobile payments, digital methods in banking, Aadhaar linked accounts, AI powered financial services has completely changed the way consumers utilize the financial services. UPI has undoubtedly been the key driver in this transformative journey which made the digital transactions widely accepted. Moreover Government initiatives have also played a critical role in this financial inclusion and fintech adoption like PMJDY, demonetization, digital lending regulations etc. UPI from 2016 has revolutionized real time transactions. In 2017 digital wallets like Paytm, PhonePe, and Google Pay gained massive adoption. In the year 2020, COVID-19 accelerated digital transactions, with UPI crossing 2 billion monthly transactions. During the year 2021, NPCI International Payments Limited (NPIL) has unlocked Cross-border UPI transactions through strategic partnerships with international payment systems. In 2022, UPI 123Pay enabled payments via feature phones (without the internet). UPI-linked RuPay Credit Cards allowed credit transactions via UPI. In 2023, UPI Lite was launched for small-value offline payments (under ₹200). International expansion continued with France, Sri Lanka, and Singapore accepting UPI and in 2024, more than 15 billion UPI transactions per month, with further expansion planned in Gulf countries and Europe. UPI Lite expanded its load money up to ₹2000. Data privacy and cyber security remain major worries, as growing volumes of

financial data are collected and shared across banks, fintech, and third-party service providers, increasing the impact of any data breach (Sharanraj, S. M. 2025).

2.2 Conceptual Framework of Digital Banking

Digital Banking means automating conventional banking through digital platforms like the internet and the enabled systems like mobile devices. Digital banking means you can avail banking services at the fingertips, all year round, irrespective of national or bank holidays. Digital banking provides us the hassle-free experience of banking services at the comfort of our home as we do not have to visit the bank every time. Digital Banking is cost affective, the data is stored digitally which eliminates the traditional banking system of long queues for data entering and updating every time consumer deposit or debit the cash or any other documentation related to the banking services. As the data is stored digitally consumers do not have to worry about any record keeping or safe guarding the documents as well and on the other hand even for the bankers it's easy to navigate the data digitally in one click.

Digital banking provides consumers 24/7 support by the use of smartphone only. UPI is one of the most widely accepted modes of digital payment method in India. Consumers are also using the digital wallets as well e.g. Paytm. Traditional methods such as NEFT, RTGS and IMPS are also used by consumers through banking applications. The emergence of neo-banks is also offering fully digital banking services. CBDC i.e. Central Bank Digital Currency has also been released by RBI recently to achieve the goal of cashless Country.

Main types of digital banking are as follows:

- **Internet Banking:** In internet banking the consumer avails banking services through the use of computer website. It's like we are at bank through our computer screens. Consumers can transfer money, check for any deduction, avail mobile passbook and pay bills etc. Consumer is needed to create a username and password to login as it contains confidential data of the respective person e.g. sbi.co.in.
- **Mobile Banking:** Mobile banking as the name suggests it's like using the bank services through the mobile phone via an app. It's quite similar as the internet banking but the device is mobile phone. It's more convenient as everyone carry their phones with them all the time. In it consumer has to download the app and register for the mobile banking of respective bank e.g. YONO app of SBI.

- **UPI:** UPI is most widely accepted mode of digital banking as it only requires the consumers registered mobile number. There is no need to remember the IFSC code or account number as well. It provides 24/7 services e.g. scan the QR code for payment instantly.
- **Digital Wallets/ E-Wallets:** Digital wallets act like a digital purse on your phone. Consumer is required to add the money first in the digital wallet and then can use that money to pay. The only difference between UPI and the Digital wallet is this that the money is in the wallet not transacted directly through the bank as in case of UPI e.g. Paytm wallet, Amazon Pay.
- **ATM / Debit & Credit Cards:** Debit Cards use your own money from your bank accounts while the credit card uses the bank's money which the consumer repays later. Debit card and credit cards are physical cards used for transaction of money or on online shopping or in physical shops as well. Consumer can use it by swiping or entering its details. RuPay is India's own card like Visa and MasterCard.
- **NEFT / RTGS / IMPS:** In NEFT the money is not sent instantly as it takes almost 2 hours. It's good for normal transfer procedures. It works on banking hours only. RTGS is used for the big transfers as minimum 2 lakh rupees transfer. It is fast within 30 minutes the transfer completes. It is used mostly by businesses. IMPS are for instant transfer of money. It works for 24/7 including holidays. It is faster than the NEFT but the amount transferable is smaller than the RTGS.
- **Neo Banks:** Neo banks are the banks that only exist on the internet. They do not have any physical branch. So that's why everything is done online through apps or websites. It is more cost effective than the traditional banks. Its targets are the young and the tech savvy customers e.g. Jupiter, Fi Money, Niyto in India. For licensing purpose they have to partner with the existing banks.
- **CBDC / Digital Rupee:** RBI has recently launched the digital version of Indian rupee. It is like cash but in the digital form. Government has said that it is 100% safe. It is fully regulated unlike crypto currency. It is looking like the future of Indian currency.

2.2.1 Definitions and Core Dimensions of Digital Banking:

This paper has provided the detailed understanding of the concept of digital banking, its evolution, trends and challenges. Secondary data analysis is done for the research purpose. Digital Banking is an umbrella term for the banking services and products which are made

available through electronic mediums such as the Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), the telephone, the internet, the social media, the mobile phone, etc. The banking industry in India is progressively expanding. The liberalization of the economy has created a competitive culture that has taken the banking sector by storm. In the survey report of “The new digital tipping point”, the number of customers using online and mobile channels, to use financial services is increasing every day. The author has discussed about the ATMs, ECS i.e. electronic clearing services, NACH i.e. National Automated Clearing House, Credit/ Debit Cards, Immediate Payment Service (IMPS), National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT), mobile banking and UPI. What limits the digitalization is the lack of internet connection and smart devices in the rural places in India also the digital literacy is very low among people (Sharma et al., 2017).

2.2.2 Service Migration from Traditional to Digital Channels:

It's a qualitative study to analyse the role of in branch efforts of banks on migrating customers from traditional branch banking to digital banking. The approach is qualitative in nature by conducting the face to face interviews to collect response from respondents. In India almost every bank provides the digital banking facility to its customers. India has seen a massive growth in digital banking acceptance post demonetization as the advent of UPI has created history which took the future of digital banking like a storm in India. In India the challenge was not only the shift from the traditional banking to the digital banking adoption of the consumers but also bringing the unbanked population of India into the system. And for that case digital banking has really done great in bringing a remarkable level of increase in the financial inclusion by bringing 51% to 69% according to the Global Findex Database 2017. At the level of banks it is understood that when the branch staff is well equipped with the soft skills and competencies in technology that also improves the banking experience of the customers. However it was observed that in public sector banks there was no special desk for relationship manager and public advisory services present unlike in private sector banks which should be considered (Kaur et al., 2021).

2.2.3 Consumer Adoption and Behaviour Model:

This paper aims to study the behavioural intentions in adopting the digital payment methods. The technique of meta-analysis has been used as it is of paramount importance in social sciences, and it binds together the results of multiple scientific studies. Digital Banking is a broader concept that is reshaping the banking system in a positive manner. Mobile banking

and online banking are the two prominent digital channels along with telephone banking, debit / credit card banking channels. After COVID-19, digital banking gained global importance as there were no other way left to use or avail the financial services but by digital means only. The demonetization by Indian Government and also the emerging technologies like 4G also paved its way to widely acceptance of digital banking in India. The models like TAM i.e. technology acceptance model have emerged as the most successful model in behavioural acceptance of consumers to any tech service. Well it has to be coupled with other factors also for the successful acceptance of new emerging technologies in digital banking (Sharma et al., 2022).

2.2.4 Artificial Intelligence in Finance:

The author has studied the impact of AI in the banking industry. The data collection is done mainly by secondary and primary means, AI adoption surveys and executive interviews were conducted. The Indian banking sector has been at the lead of accepting advanced technologies and including them in the banking system. AI powered technologies has helped in cutting down the operational costs in banks. Undoubtedly these technological advancements are also helpful in the detection of frauds, maintaining the transparency and increasing the security as well. Banks can process the record level high speeding data through the help of the digital banking systems and reduce time span for particular tasks to complete. One of the most popular theories of technology acceptance is technology acceptance model (TAM), which emphasizes on the two important factors influencing a person's intention to use new technology perceived usefulness and ease of use. The National Institution for Transforming India (NITI Aayog) has also developed an "AI for All" strategy to use AI for inclusive growth in various sectors such as banking sector, education. What still limits the AI powered banking is lack of high quality relevant data that can train AI models for banking industry because of the crucial data safety and security as well (Pahari et al., 2023).

So we can say that digital banking in India has evolved drastically in last 2 decades providing a wide range of services like internet banking, mobile banking, UPI, digital wallets and recently introduced Central Bank Digital Currency. Many authors have highlighted the points where it came into the mainstream banking and took it over completely. This conceptual understanding of the digital banking will definitely help learners to understand the emerging trends, impacts of digital banking and its challenges as well.

2.3 Impact of Digital Banking in India:

Over the last decade India has observed a revolutionary change in financial sector due to the fast growing technology and introduction of digital tools. The shift that has occurred from traditional banking to digital banking has created a profound impact in Indian economy and its rural and urban population. Digital banking and services not only made the banking facilities available to all at one click but it has a very important role in financial inclusion and economic growth of the country. As the technological advancements occur many applications like YONO by State Bank of India, Paytm, PhonePe and Google Pay has completely changed the way consumers used to avail banking services and conduct their daily transactions. The impact of these digital initiatives has filled the gap between the rural and urban banking a lot and has brought millions of unbanked citizens into the financial system. We can say that the major impacts which digital banking have are – Financial inclusion, economic growth, customer convenience, cost effective, increased efficiency of banks and empowerment of businesses and consumers.

Many Indian banks have launched their digital banking applications for the ease of the consumers and for making the banking services reach everyone easily. Some of the official digital applications launched by different banks are:

Public Sector Banks:

Bank	App Name	Launch Year
SBI	YONO SBI	2017
Bank of Baroda	Bob World	2021
Punjab National Bank	PNB One	2021
Canara Bank	Candi	2020
Union Bank	Union Mobile	2018
Indian Bank	IndOASIS	2019
UCO Bank	UCO mBanking Plus	2019

Private Sector Banks:

Bank	App Name	Launch Year
HDFC Bank	HDFC Mobile Banking	2010
ICICI Bank	iMobile Pay	2008
Axis Bank	Axis Mobile	2013
Kotak Bank	Kotak Mobile Banking	2012
Yes Bank	YES Mobile	2015

Payment Banks:

Bank	App Name
Paytm Payments Bank	Paytm
Airtel Payments Bank	Airtel Thanks
India Post Payments Bank	IPPB Mobile App

Among all the digital banking initiatives in India the **Unified Payments Interface** commonly known as **UPI** has come up as the most accepted digital initiative in the history of Indian banking. UPI was launched by NPCI in the year 2016 for instant transactions between the different banks through a mobile app only without any long process. Earlier payment methods like NEFT and RTGS required account numbers and IFCS codes while in case of UPI these steps were not needed only the customer's mobile number, or the UPI QR code generated by their UPI app. Also a virtual payment address was also provided for the transfer of funds. UPI experienced the most transformative growth after demonetization and COVID 19 which forced Indian to shift from traditional banking ways to digital ways and there the UPI wave occurred. From urban businesses to rural farmers, from larger retailers to small vendors and even vegetable sellers UPI became the first choice for transfer of funds. It democratized digital payments across all sections of society. By 2023 UPI had process over 10 billion transactions per month making India the largest real time digital platform in the entire world even surpassing the developed countries like USA an United kingdoms. UPI success has made other countries to adopt it including Singapore, France, UAE and United Kingdom allowing the Indians to make payments abroad as well.

UPI was made more accessible to common people the government when it launched its own UPI based application called **BHIM** i.e. Bharat Interface for Money on 30 December 2016, it was developed by National Payments Corporation of India. It was named after Dr BR Ambedkar. BHIM is a government owned UPI based application available in 20 Indian languages for the ease of the Indian diverse linguistic population. BHIM has recorded over 80 million downloads till its launch.

UPI and BHIM have made digital payments for smartphone users easy across India, there was another initiative known as **AePS** i.e. Aadhaar Enabled Payment System which was developed by NPCI launched in 2016. Its main objective was to make digital payment services available to rural India as not everyone carries the smartphone. AePS digital payment system allows individuals to conduct basic banking transactions using only their Aadhaar number and biometric fingerprint authentication. AePS doesn't require smartphone internet connection or even basic literacy which helps to include the rural old age population avail the financial services easily e.g. if a rural senior citizen got old age pension be it Rs 1500 he/she can withdraw it only using their biometric authentication and Aadhaar number. So AePS is a practical approach by NPCI for the inclusion of rural remote villages bringing basic financial service to their doorstep. This service successfully helped in implementing the governments Direct Benefit Transfer scheme to most vulnerable group of individuals by preventing the benefits from being exploited by any corruption or middleman interference.

2.3.1 Policy – Driven Inclusion:

The NITI Aayog Perspective:

This report from NITI Aayog 2022 Section II gives the developments in the area of financial inclusion in India catalysed by PMJDY and India stack. Small financial banks (SFBs) could leverage low cost deposit to lend to micro, small and medium sized businesses to enhance financial inclusion as they will get the benefit of banking licence. Small finance banks have to maintain at least 50 % of the loan portfolio in ticket size of ₹ 2.5 million and below. When these reforms were on-going, the digital India revolution actually catalysed by PMJDY, India stack, e- KYC and UPI. More than 400 million bank accounts were opened under PMJDY scheme which achieved remarkable growth in financial inclusion by bringing unbanked population to the banked consumers. Even after these reforms a lot of small scale businesses still struggled to get benefits from these schemes which needs to be addressed (NITI Aayog report, 2022).

2.3.2 Financial Inclusion and Digital Accessibility in Rural India:

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis and role of digital payments in the financial inclusion promotion in rural India. For the collection of data secondary resources, empirical study and regional case studies are done by the author. India's digital payment advancements has rally created a significant impact on the rural population. RBI has released the financial inclusion index (FI-Index) report that observed 67.0 in March 2025 with a noticeable 24.3% increase from the year 2021. Rural population was always lacking behind in becoming the part of mainstream banking system of India and devoid of the financial benefits so far. But after the government initiatives such as Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), Aadhaar enabled Payment Systems (AePS), Unified Payments Interface (UPI), mobile wallets the financial inclusion in rural India has seen a remarkable growth. These schemes proved to be the new pathways to bridge the gaps of financial divide. As of 2025 account ownership in India has reached from 35% in 2011 to 89% in 2025 with maximum rural India contribution in in new account openings. Under Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana over 55.98 crore accounts have been opened, comprising a significant number of rural accounts i.e. 67% with 56% held by women. Bank Mitras (banking correspondents) have also been deployed to provide last mile services. As of December 2024, 107 digital banking units established offering a range of digital banking services in rural and semi urban areas. Evolution of digital payment systems such as Unified Payment Interfaces (UPI), Mobile wallets and Fintech initiatives such as Paytm, PhonePe, Google Pay and Amazon Pay have also made it easier for rural and semi urban population to be the part of growing digital banking system in India. The challenge that still holds rest of the rural population back is lack of internet connectivity, digital literacy, security/trust issues and technical errors (Behara, N. 2026).

2.3.3 Economic Growth and the Digitalization of Industry:

In this paper the author examines the impact of digitalization on the economic growth in India. Data collection resources are secondary in nature but from the credible resources including Reserve Bank of India (RBI), World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the Telecom Regularity Authority of India (TRAI). The methodology followed in econometric techniques such as regression analysis and cointegration models. With the digital infrastructure expansion such as internet penetration, broadband access it leads to digital financial system growth such as mobile banking, digital payments which leads to business

innovations like E-commerce, digital platforms, start-ups and ultimately it leads to the economic growth of the country. As in India too have experience GDP growth, productivity and employment. In the study also the correlation analysis shows the positive relationship between digitalization indicators and economic growth. Digital payments have the strongest correlation with GDP growth. The study still shows gaps in digital literacy and policy recommendations for the improved digital and economic growth (Chitra, M., & Mahato, M. 2026).

2.3.4 Behavioural Impact – Customer Satisfaction and User Experience:

The research paper explores the customer satisfaction with respect to digital banking in India. Main sources of data collection are surveys, secondary data sources and literature. Digital banking from traditional banking shift was a long process in which government initiatives like Digital India, Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), demonetization, introduction of Unified Payment Interface (UPI) have played a key role. Customer satisfaction in banking is deeply rooted in quality of service provided and technology adoption theories. SERVQUAL model evaluates service quality in five dimensions i.e. reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness. Another model TAM i.e. Technology Acceptance model advocates that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use determine customer acceptance of technology. Customers opt for online platforms of payments when they find them useful and easy to use and navigate. Another theory is Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT) in context to digital banking this theory suggests that customer's satisfaction depends on their expectations met by the actual performance. The fast growing digital banking confirms the satisfaction of the consumers as it is 24/7 service, it's easy to use, it doesn't need any IFSC code or account numbers for sending money to anyone which helped a lot in the enhanced use of these services. Since most of the data available discussed mainly the success of UPI with less focus on digital credit and AI based services (Jogdand, M., & Jagdale, P. 2026).

2.3.5 Operational Transformation and Efficiency in the Banking Sector:

It is important to look at more than just a customer's point of view. While the previous paper studies the user satisfaction, we should also focus on the impact of digital banking in the internal banking of the banks themselves. For this context the research studies the impact of digitalization on Indian banking industry with a focus on improvement of operational efficiency. The research done is descriptive in nature and follows reliable secondary data

sources. Digital banking technologies such as mobile banking, internet banking, digital payment methods are playing a critical role in reducing the operational cost at the banks. These technological advancements have noticeable benefits such as remote transactions, less paper work, reduced need of physical branches and decreased operational expenses. Digitalization of banking services has also made the competitive advantages in the banking sector as due to latest technological expansions even the banking sector also has to be in synchronization with the technology to be in the race. However with the surge of digitalization also raises a concern of its impact on employment in banking sector. Well these are just uncertainty interpretations as by the expansion of AI models in banking sector, does it have the capability of displacing human jobs too. But as of now there is lack of digital literacy among the rural India and also in semi urban areas too which still creates a gap and need of more digital awareness solutions to be implemented in the society. There is also a need of skilled staff in the banking sector which should be comfortable in learning new skills as it is the need of the hour (Shaikh et al., 2025).

2.3.6 Micro Enterprise Transformation – Impacts on Small Businesses:

The author has explained the impact of digital payment methods on the small businesses in India. The study has followed a descriptive and analytical design to examine the impact of UPI i.e. Unified Payment Interface on small businesses in India. Primary data was collected from structured questionnaire (Google Form) distributed both online and offline to the small business owners, vendors and service providers. The author has concluded from the studies that a very high proportion of respondents (85%) reported an enhanced sale after the adoption of UPI (Unified Payment Interface) which clearly shows the positive impact of digital payment methods on small businesses. The interpretations from the chi square test also indicate that there is statistically significant association between the level of adoption of Unified Payment Interface (UPI) with the improvement in small business performance. The study has only focused on the role of UPI as a digital payment method and not concentrated on the other digital payment methods (Sinha & Moid, 2026).

After summarizing the key research articles on the impact of digital banking at different levels we understood that digital banking is not only now limited to bank to phone/mobile banking but it has grown beyond that. This transformative journey of digital banking initiated by government led schemes like Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY); Aadhaar enabled Payment System (AePS), Unified Payment Interface (UPI). These initiatives just

changed the way rural, urban and semi urban consumers do the transactions. The economic boost that came after the advent of these schemes was noticeable. How the growth of payment gateways occur afterwards and people chosen them with open hands showed the customer satisfaction to the digital tools in modern banking. Digital Banking has not only impacted the way consumers interacted but changed the way that how bankers used to work , they also have to shift their traditional ways of working to tech savvy digital methods and that helped them a lot in cutting the operational costs, reducing the paper work, keeping the record and many more. With the AI chatbot in banking application it has become more convenient for the consumers to understand digital banking and more work is going on to train these AI models for future expansion of the same in banking industry.

2.4 Trends and Challenges of Digital Banking in India:

With the rapid technological advancements and progressive government policies the digital banking landscape is also following the trends. India is witnessing the new trends in the field of digital banking as to accomplish a fully digitalized economy and banking system.

As discussed earlier the most significant trend and adoption is observed in the success of Unified Payment Interface (UPI) till its launch. UPI has uncertainly put India as the largest real time digital payment market in the world. The introduction of the Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) commonly known as the Digital Rupee by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) in 2022 represents another landmark development in banking evolution. Now the evolution of AI i.e. Artificial Intelligence, rise of neo banking, open banking frameworks are also pushing Indian banking towards a more innovative future and customer centric approach.

Where there are remarkable technological advancements in digital banking in India, there are several substantial challenges that also exist which need time to time check so that they do not create potential hurdle in the path of modern banking system both at the end of consumer and banks. Challenges like cybersecurity threats and digital frauds are increasing day by day putting consumers and financial institutions both at risk. Low level digital literacy in rural elderly population and limited internet connectivity in rural India also proven to be one of the major reasons of digital gap that still exists between urban and rural India and hinders the widespread adoption of digital banking across country.

A critical analysis of these emerging trends and the challenges is very important for the policy makers and regulatory bodies to frame or develop comprehensive solutions for the better adoption of these emerging trends in digital banking without any fear among the consumers.

2.4.1 Trends in Digital Banking in India:

According to the report of RBI on 29 December 2025 i.e. Trend and Progress of Banking India 2024-2025 states that technological innovations are reshaping the financial services landscape. The digital public infrastructure (DPI) is providing base for rapid financial innovations and playing a major role in acknowledging barriers to inclusion. Fintech is also acting in reducing the digital divide in the rural and urban population. **HaRBInger** initiative by Reserve Bank of India (RBI) is a strategic trend in Indian regulation which is an innovative approach by hosting global hackathons to solve critical banking hurdles. The Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) / Digital rupee is also evolving as an important instrument within digital banking recent trend. Government is also pushing fintech in the banking sector as its ease of doing, even at the level of banking reducing operational cost. Automation of credit appraisal and know your customer (KYC) through AI reduces cost, accelerates disbursement, and enables small loans in remote regions. Though these emerging technological trends are very helpful but along with these key challenges such as digital trust and frauds remain major concern (Reserve Bank of India, 2025).

The author has studied the Indian banking transformation driven by digitalization, fintech collaboration, involvement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and financial inclusion initiatives in India. This study employs a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative research techniques to analyse the evolving banking landscape in India. The methodology includes primary data collection through surveys and interviews with banking professionals and customers, as well as secondary data analysis of financial reports, government publications, and banking databases. According to the author the most significant initiative by RBI is introduction of Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC). Along with it the rise of neo-banks which are fully digital banks that operate without any need of a physical branch setup. These digital only banks serve different customer segment e.g. consumer neo banks like Fi Money and Jupiter (each backed by Federal Bank) offer zero balance saving accounts. There are another neo banks also for different segments of people which are Niyoo offering multicurrency forex card, Mahila Money focuses on women entrepreneurs (by

NBFC tie up). It is found that 68% of banks use AI for predictive analytics, AI-based credit scoring lowers default rates by 15%. Sustainable green banking is also a good initiative as it focuses on environmental responsibility and social impact e.g. YES bank's green bond initiative funded over 20 renewable green projects in India. Though sustainable banking has rapid growth but the initial cost is very high as renewable resources and infrastructure require significant capital investment. There is limited public awareness to these new initiatives as well. There should be good digital literacy to understand all these new initiatives and to protect oneself from cybersecurity frauds as well (Shekhar, 2025).

2.4.2 Challenges in Digital Banking in India:

The study identifies the challenges faced by consumers and the banks in successful adoption of digital banking. The data is taken from the secondary sources like published research papers, annual reports of the bank and various government bodies like RBI reports, NITI Aayog report. Challenges which are faced by the customers in adopting digital banking are related to the security of their transactions and personal data. Many consumers lack digital literacy and find it difficult to use the digital banking services especially in rural areas which still create a divide between rural and urban population. Internet connectivity is among the challenges which make it difficult to use digital services in the rural areas and difficult geographic areas. On the other hand banks also face regulatory challenges in applying the RBI guidelines in certain situations. Cybersecurity challenges are faced by banks as the AI is developing fast so the hackers are also proving to be a threat to banks and consumers. There should be adequate measures in improved cybersecurity, enhanced digital literacy in rural areas for which banks should organize digital literacy camps (Maniyar & Ramgopal, 2025).

The main objective of the author for this study is to highlight the digital transformation of financial sector analyzing the evolution its issues and challenges. The study is based on the data derived from the secondary sources. The use of digital methods has revolutionized the Indian financial industry. Innovations like mobile wallets, fintech ecosystem and digital lending platforms has changed the way consumers used to do transactions earlier. It has no doubt pushed our economy towards more advances and tech savvy cashless economy. Though with these advancements there comes a lot of challenges also in fully adoption of these services and implementing financial inclusion. Some of the key challenges are cybersecurity issues including phishing, malware; hacking attempts can compromise the security of online transactions. In rural and semi urban areas due to lack of digital literacy

people easily fall for these online security threats. UPI like any other online transaction technology also experience technical glitches and its dependency on smartphones also keep the people devoid of these services who doesn't have smartphone. Fake apps and websites can also steal user's confidential data. These challenges still make it difficult to adopt fully digitalized banking services among people and create a digital divide in rural and urban population. This study is primarily based on the data taken from the secondary sources only so the results can be subjective to the researcher as well (Chaddha & Jain, 2024).

To summarize the literature review we can say that undoubtedly there are many initiatives that Indian government has been taking for digitalization of the bank services across India and same for the financial inclusion. But with the emerging new technologies there are new threats as well. Some challenges also like digital literacy is not same across India so still the digital divide occurs. Though bank branches has been expanded in the rural areas but lack of basic literacy makes it difficult even for bankers to make general public understand the new age digital banking system.

Digital banking awareness camps are also necessary for the rural population of India as they are most vulnerable to cybersecurity threats than the urban population which has some knowledge about the digital services. The digital tools which are developing should also be developed in a way that they must be adopted by the whole country and not a section of people.

The interpretation from these studies suggests us that there should be **Co-Evolution** of these digital services and consumers understanding of these changing scenarios only then the optimum use of these evolving services will occur.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

This chapter is about the research data collection and methods, types of data collected in the research process, data collection methods that were used during the research, sampling techniques tools used in the detailed study of Impact of Digital Banking in India. The methodology adopted in this study and findings are reliable valid and relevant to the research objectives.

3.1 Research Design:

The research follows a mixed-method research design, which includes both qualitative and quantitative approach to analyze impact of digital banking in India its trends and challenges. The nature of it is exploratory because it explores the emerging trends in digital banking in India, its conceptual framework, customer's experience, impact on small businesses, operational challenges of digital banking through literature review. An interview is conducted with the bank manager (UCO Bank) and the bank staff and open ended responses. At the same time descriptive because it describes the patterns of digital banking usage, frequency of digital services, challenges of using digital services and benefits of using it through a structured questionnaire with close ending questions distributed online through whatsapp medium to the diverse age group of people.

The study uses both primary data (information collectedly in person by interview and questionnaire) and secondary data (information already published by other scholars, authors from RBI reports etc.). This is how it makes the findings more complete and balanced in nature. The main objective of this research is to understand that what impact digital banking services have created in India, what are the recent trends and the challenges faced by it.

3.2 Type of Data:

The study is based on two types of data i.e. primary data and secondary data.

3.2.1 Primary Data

The primary data is the data that is collected at firsthand, the sources for primary data are:

- **Structured Questionnaire** via Google Forms with 59 responses. The questionnaire contained 15 questions covering-

- Demographic information mainly age group, occupation of the respondent and educational qualification of the respondent.
 - Digital banking usage pattern covering questions related to use of digital banking services, preferred digital banking service and frequency of using digital banking services.
 - The next section of questions cover the impact of digital banking services comprising of questions related to convenience of using the digital banking services, impact of digital banking on the dependency of cash, how accessible are digital bank services and how effectively it reduces the transaction cost of the consumers.
 - In this section the questions are about the challenges faced by the consumers in operating the digital banking services and how secure they feel while using the digital banking services.
 - The last section of questions cover the general opinions and satisfaction level of the consumers including the digital banking and its impact on financial inclusion in the country and the satisfaction level of the consumers after using the digital banking services.
- **Interview** conducted with the staff and the branch manager of UCO Bank. The interview was semi structured, using set of prepared questions for getting the insight on specific issues with open ended answers. Topics covered in the interview are-
 - How banks play part in the promotion of the digital banking services among general people.
 - What are the observed trends in the behavior of the customers in relation to branch experience verses the experience after using digital services.
 - Operational challenges from the perspective of bank such as fraud cases, customers complaints, technology failures and staff training etc.
 - Suggestion for the further improvement in the implication of the digital banking services like better security, awareness programs and policy support.

The primary data is mainly **quantitative** in nature (from the questionnaire) but also include the qualitative inputs from the interview and open ended responses.

3.2.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data was collected from various published and online sources to provide the background, conceptual framework, recent advances, contextual findings and support to the primary findings for the research project.

Sources for the secondary data include:

- Academic journal articles on digital banking, UPI, Digital payment systems in India, fintech and AI introduction in Indian banking.
- Books and reports on banking services, financial technology, and digital transformation in India.
- Official publications from RBI, NPCI, NITI Aayog and other government bodies related to the government policies, initiatives for the financial inclusion in India and digital banking services.
- Annual reports of banks.
- News articles on cybersecurity and fraud trends.

Secondary data helped in the understanding of the research project impact of digital banking in India, its background, historical evolution of banking and the transformation from the traditional banking to the digital banking system. With the help of review articles understanding of the recent trends in banking UPI, digital payment applications, neo banking and mobile banking adoption was done. It has helped in studying the challenges like cybersecurity threats, fraud cases and creating the correlation between the primary data with the already available secondary data sources.

3.3 Data Collection Methods:

For the collection of the data three methods were used:

Survey method using Questionnaire: Primary quantitative data was collected through a structured questionnaire created with the help of Google Forms. It was online survey based and self-administered.

- The questionnaire was shared through the online mode by whatsapp and email to target the wider range of consumers.
- Most of the questions were close ended questions including multiple choice questions, checkbox and Likert-scale for the purpose of easy statistical analysis.

- Content of the questionnaire has 15 structured questions divided in five sections according to the context of the questions asked. The sections are as follows:
 - ❖ Section A : Demographic Information
 - ❖ Section B : Digital Banking Usage Pattern
 - ❖ Section C : Impact of Digital Banking
 - ❖ Section D : Challenges of Digital Banking
 - ❖ Section E : General Opinion and satisfaction

Personal Interview: A personal interview was conducted with the staff and the branch manager of UCO Bank Nakodar (Punjab). The interview was semi structured with open end answers to get the insight of digital banking at the end of bank or financial institution and the issues faced by them. Topics discussed were:

- Digital banking strategy by bank and the adoption rate by consumers.
- Consumer's feedback to the digital banking services and their complaint patterns.
- Fraud incidents faced by the consumers and the security management practices.
- Challenges faced by banks related to the infrastructure and technology related challenges.

Notes were taken during the interview with the bank manager and the staff then later summarized for the qualitative analysis.

Secondary Sources Analysis: Secondary data was collected through the document analysis of sources like:

- Research papers and analytical reports.
- RBI circular, policy documents, online authorized publications related to digital banking, financial inclusion and fintech in banking services.
- Annual reports from the official websites of certain banks.

By the help of secondary data a correlation with the primary data can be observed and validation of certain facts is done.

3.4 Sampling Design:

The target population for this study includes bank customers in India who use digital banking services occasionally or repetitively and banking professionals who handle digital banking operations are customer services. The study focuses on urban and semi urban areas (Nakodar, Jalandhar) where digital banking adoption is relatively higher.

Sample size includes a total number of 59 respondents to the structured questionnaire via Google Forms. 5 staff members including the bank manager of the UCO Bank Nakodar gave the interview.

This sample size proved to be adequate for the exploratory and descriptive study for the topic impact of digital banking in India its recent trends and challenges.

3.5 Sampling Technique:

Convenience sampling for questionnaire was done. Respondents were selected on their willingness to participate and the ease of access (friends, family, colleagues, acquaintance, whatsapp groups and bank customers encountered in the field).

Purposive sampling for the interview is done. UCO Bank manager and the staff were selected purposely for their real time experience in dealing with the customers on a daily basis and their familiarity with the digital banking services.

While this sampling enhances practicality and feasibility, it may limit the generalization of entire Indian banking system due to a particular area analysis while it has contributed in the exploratory research for the project.

3.6 Tools Used for Data Collection and Analysis:

Data Collection Tools:

- Google Forms used to design, share and collect responses for the online questionnaire.
- Interview Schedule for a semi structured interview with the bank staff and bank manager. Notebook used to record the interview responses.
- Laptop and internet services used for accessing the literature, downloading the resources online and for the preparation of the report.

Software and Technology Used:

- Google Forms for the creation of questionnaire and basic response summaries.
- Microsoft Excel for organizing data, calculating the frequencies, percentage and running the chi square test.
- Microsoft Word for writing and formatting the entire project report.

3.7 Statistical Techniques Used:

Since the study involves quantitative survey data statistical techniques used to analyze the results.

- **Descriptive statistics** were used to summarize the data collected from the 59 respondent samples from the questionnaire. It included frequency and percentage used to describe demographic variables and response patterns. MS Excel was used for these statistic studies.
- **Chi-Square Test of Independence** was done to examine if consumer's age group has any different influence on how they perceive the convenience of digital banking utilities. This inferential methodology was applied directly to a cross-tabulated contingency matrix matching the respondent's age demographics (from below 18 to above 50) against the specific rating on transaction convenience and time saving benefits.

Evaluated at a standard baseline of $\alpha = 0.05$ via MS Excel, the test yielded a clear p-value of **0.469**. Because this result is greater than the standard significance value 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), the study fails to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) suggesting that the two variables remain statistically independent.

3.8 Reliability and Validity:

Validity:

- The questionnaire and interview schedule were developed on the basis of existing literature, RBI related guidelines and expert input. It was taken care of to include questions covering impact, trends and challenges of digital banking.
- Questions stated were in clear language and the layout was logical, easy to follow making it clear for the respondent that what each question intends to measure.
- Abstract concepts were measured using multiple related questions which improve the robustness of the measurement.

Reliability:

- The questionnaire, interview guide and the coding procedures are clearly documented to be relying on.
- Responses from the Google Forms were exported and saved, so that the data can be reexamined.

Ethical Consideration and Data quality:

- Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study, and the participation was voluntary.
- No personal identifiers were collected; all responses were treated anonymously for the unbiased interpretation.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis and Interpretation

This chapter presents a brief analysis and interpretation of both secondary and primary data to evaluate the trends and impact of digital banking. Secondary data has helped to understand the macro level digital trends. The chapter also evaluates the primary data collected through a structured questionnaire alongside in depth interview with a branch manager and bank staff. The objective of this dual approach is to align the nationwide digital trends with ground level realities. The data is presented through tables, charts and descriptive statistics, followed by brief interpretation.

4.1 Macro Analysis of Digital Banking Trends in India (Secondary Data)

It is essential to look at the digital transaction volumes at the broad level for contextualization of study. The given table outlines the monthly growth of Bharat Interface for Money-Unified Payments Interface (BHIM-UPI) transactions over a period of 12 months serving a benchmark for national digital banking adoption.

Table S1: Monthly Growth of BHIM-UPI Transactions (FY 2022-2023)

Sr. No.	Month	Volume of Transactions (in lakhs)
1	Apr-22	55830
2	May-22	59553
3	Jun-22	58627
4	Jul-22	58638
5	Aug-22	65795
6	Sep-22	65537
7	Oct-22	73053
8	Nov-22	70733
9	Dec-22	78297
10	Jan-23	80367
11	Feb-23	75346
12	Mar-23	90629

Source: Ministry of electronics and Information Technology (MeitY), DigiDhan Dashboard

Data Interpretation: The data presented in the Table S1 indicates a robust upward trajectory in the adoption of BHIM-UPI transactions in India. In April 2022, the transaction volume stood at 55830 lakh but by the close of financial year in March 2023 a drastic increase occurred in the transaction volume at 90629 lakh representing the overall volume growth of approximately 62.3% in just one year.

While the data has shown a steady growth, minor fluctuations are also observed in the data in the month of June 2022 and November 2022. However by the end of fiscal year in March 2023 a sharp jump in the transactions is observed to 90629 lakh suggesting an overall wide adoption of digital banking system.

This macro level study provides solid empirical evidence that digital banking has become the part and parcel of the daily lives of consumers across India.

4.2 Demographic profile of Respondents (Primary Data)

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by age group (N = 59)

Age group	Frequency	Percentage
Below 18 years	1	1.7%
18–25 years	6	10.2%
26–35 years	45	76.3%
36–50 years	4	6.8%
Above 50 years	3	5.1%

Interpretation: As shown in Table 1, the majority of the respondents belong to the 26-35 years age group which indicates that the digital banking services are predominantly used by the working age adults. The next second largest section is of 18-25 years age group indicating young adults and students using the digital banking services while the older age groups are relatively low. This shows that the digital banking adoption is higher in the young professionals and early career adults.

Figure 1: Age-group distribution of respondents (pie chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The pie chart reflects the same pattern i.e. 26-35 years age group dominates the sample, which align with the interpretation that this group is more tech savvy and uses more digital services than the rest.

Table 2: Occupation of respondents (N = 59)

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Student	5	8.5%
Salaried Employee	31	52.5%
Business Owner	4	6.8%
Homemaker	13	22.0%
Other	6	10.2%

Interpretation: Salaried employees form the largest occupational group (52.5%), indicating that the digital banking services are predominantly used by working professionals. Even homemakers (22.0%) and students (8.5%) have also significant contribution in the adoption of digital banking services.

Figure 2: Occupational distribution of respondents (pie chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

This pie chart presenting the occupational distribution of respondents aligns perfectly with the findings of Table 1 showing that the salaried employees are the most frequent users of digital banking services.

Table 3: Educational qualification of the respondents (N = 59)

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Below HSC	1	1.7%
12th Pass	2	3.4%
Graduate	23	39.0%
Postgraduate	33	55.9%

Interpretation: Table 3 shows the educational qualification of the respondents indicating that majority of them are post graduates (55.9%), followed by graduates (39.0%) and few are 12th pass or below. It represents that section using the digital banking services is well educated and so is their understanding towards the changing trends in digital services. Very few respondents are 12th pass or less which shows very less usage of digital banking services.

Figure 3: Educational qualification of respondents (pie chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

This pie chart shows that the post graduates form the highest educational segment proving that digital banking services are mostly used by highly educated people.

4.3 Digital Banking Usage Patterns

Table 4: Use of digital banking services (N = 59)

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	56	94.9%
No	3	5.1%

Interpretation: This Table suggests that the vast majority of respondents (94.9%) utilize digital banking services. It suggests very high adoption of digital banking services in the sample which shows that it has become the preferred mode for transaction among users.

Figure 4: Usage of digital banking services (pie chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

This pie chart suggests that almost every respondent is using some digital banking service, as 94.9% of total respondents have said yes to the use of digital banking services which shows wide acceptance for the digital banking services in India.

Table 5: Most used digital banking service (N = 59)

Service	Frequency	Percentage
UPI (PhonePe/Google Pay/Paytm)	54	91.5%
Mobile banking app	3	5.1%
Internet banking	0	0.0%
Debit/credit card	2	3.4%
Digital wallet	0	0.0%

Interpretation: Table 5 suggests that the widely used digital banking service by respondents is UPI (PhonePe/Google Pay/Paytm) comprising 91.5% from the sample.

Figure 5: Primary digital banking service used (pie chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

This pie chart clearly indicates that UPI is one of the leading and most adopted digital banking initiative launched by our government, due to its ease of use and 24/7 availability, it's the most used digital banking channel in India.

Table 6: Frequency of digital banking usage (N = 59)

Usage Frequency	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	38	64.4%
Weekly	17	28.8%
Monthly	3	5.1%
Rarely	1	1.7%

Interpretation: Table 6 depicts that 64.4% respondents use digital banking services daily, 28.8% of respondents use digital banking services weekly and rest of the respondents (very less number) use these services weekly or rarely which suggests that digital banking has become the part of the life of consumers now. Their dependence on the cash has reduced sharply due to the advent of digital banking services.

Figure 6: Frequency of digital banking service usage (pie chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The pie chart confirms that daily use of digital banking is highest followed by weekly use which tells that how digital banking services has become the undivided part of our life and the dependency of users on it.

4.4 Impact of Digital Banking

Table 7: Respondent Opinions on the convenience of using digital banking (N = 59)

Rating (1–5)	Frequency	Percentage
5 (Strongly Agree)	35	59.3%
4 (Agree)	16	27.1%
3 (Neutral)	1	1.7%
2 (Disagree)	1	1.7%
1 (Strongly Disagree)	6	10.2%

Average rating: ≈4.24

Interpretation: Table 7 suggests that majority of the respondents (59.3%) strongly agree that digital banking has made their financial transactions more convenient and time saving, only a small fraction selected disagree or strongly disagree. It indicates that respondents perceive digital banking highly convenient and efficient.

Figure 7: Convenience and time saving impact of digital banking (bar chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The bar chart confirms that 5 star and 4 star ratings dominate confirming that users find digital banking fast and easy to use.

Table 8: Impact of digital banking on cash dependency (N = 59)

Rating (1–5)	Frequency	Percentage
5 (Strongly Agree)	34	57.6%
4 (Agree)	16	27.1%
3 (Neutral)	1	1.7%
2 (Disagree)	2	3.4%
1 (Strongly Disagree)	6	10.2%

Average rating: ≈4.19

Interpretation: Most respondents (57.6%) strongly agree that digital banking has reduced their dependency on cash, followed by respondents (27.1%) who has chosen agree to reduced dependency on cash. Only small proportion of respondents gave disagree or neutral response suggesting the sharp reduction in the dependency on cash after using digital banking services.

Figure 8: Dependency on cash versus digital banking (bar chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

This bar chart suggests that digital banking is sharply reducing the dependency on physical cash as it is the quick method for transactions, easy to use and available to people 24/7.

Table 9: Accessibility and availability of digital banking services (N = 59)

Rating (1–5)	Frequency	Percentage
5 (Strongly Agree)	35	59.3%
4 (Agree)	12	20.3%
3 (Neutral)	6	10.2%
2 (Disagree)	0	0.0%
1 (Strongly Disagree)	6	10.2%

Average rating: ≈4.19

Interpretation: Table 9 depicts that most of the respondents strongly agree (59.3%) or agree (20.3%) that digital services are available 24/7 and are easily accessible. Very less respondents chose neutral and strongly disagree suggesting that users are finding it more easy to use due to 24/7 availability of digital banking services.

Figure 9: 24/7 Availability of digital banking services (bar chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The bar chart confirms the 24/7 availability of the digital banking services as compare to the limited timings of the traditional banking services which is one of the reason for its widespread adoption.

Table 10: Impact of digital banking on transaction cost and bank visits (N = 59)

Rating (1–5)	Frequency	Percentage
5 (Strongly Agree)	30	50.8%
4 (Agree)	17	28.8%
3 (Neutral)	2	3.4%
2 (Disagree)	3	5.1%
1 (Strongly Disagree)	7	11.9%

Average rating: ≈4.02

Interpretation: Table 10 suggests that majority of respondents strongly agree (50.8%) or agree (28.8) that digital banking helped them save money on transaction and bank visits. Rest of the respondents disagree, strongly disagree or neutral about it which are less in number as compare to strongly agree and agree. So we can say digital banking has really reduced the transactional cost.

Figure 10: Savings on transactional cost and bank visits (bar chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The bar chart depicts the cost saving impact of digital banking services for respondents. User's continuous visits to bank have reduced sharply due to digital banking services.

4.5 Challenges of Digital Banking

Table 11: Challenges faced by users in digital banking (N = 59)

Challenge Type	Responses	Percentage
Cybersecurity threat or fraud	13	22%
Poor internet connectivity	23	39%
Technical errors	18	30.5%
Lack of digital literacy	5	8.5%
Trust and security concerns	14	23.7%
None of the above	18	30.5%

Interpretation: The major challenges faced by respondents are poor internet connectivity (39%) and technical errors (30.5%). For some respondents it is cybersecurity threat (22%) and for some it is trust and security concerns (23.7%). This shows that digital infrastructure and technical errors are the main challenges faced by respondents.

Figure 11: Challenges faced in digital banking service (horizontal bar chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The horizontal bar chart suggests that poor internet connectivity, technical errors, cybersecurity threats and trust security concerns are the main challenges faced by the respondents.

Table 12: Consumer satisfaction with the security of digital banking services (N = 59)

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Very satisfied	14	23.7%
Satisfied	31	52.5%
Neutral	13	22.0%
Dissatisfied	1	1.7%
Very dissatisfied	0	0.0%

Interpretation: In Table 12, majority of the respondents are very satisfied (23.7%) or satisfied (52.5%) with the security of digital banking services. Only 22.0% showed neutral response and 1.7% gave dissatisfies response. This suggests that mostly users consider digital banking services secure and as some gave neutral response which can be taken as room for improvement in security concerns.

Figure 12: Consumer satisfaction with the security of digital banking services (bar chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The bar chart shows high overall satisfaction of consumers with small segment giving neutral response in relation to the security of digital banking services.

4.6 General Opinions and Satisfaction

Table 13: Digital banking service contribution in financial inclusion in India (N = 59)

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	20	33.9%
Agree	27	45.8%
Neutral	12	20.3%
Disagree	0	0.0%
Strongly disagree	0	0.0%

Interpretation: Majority of the respondents are agree (45.2%) and strongly agree (33.9%) on digital banking's contribution in promoting the financial inclusion in India. Only 20.3% respondents selected neutral response suggesting that digital banking has played a very important role in promoting financial inclusion in India.

Figure 13: Digital banking contribution to financial inclusion (pie chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The pie chart confirms that digital banking has acted as a driver in financial inclusion in India.

Table 14: Key barriers to digital banking growth (N = 59)

Challenge	Frequency	Percentage
Cybersecurity threat	25	42.4%
Lack of internet infrastructure	4	6.8%
Low digital literacy	16	27.1%
Trust issues among users	12	20.3%
Regulatory challenges	2	3.4%

Interpretation: Cybersecurity threat (42.4%) is observed as the biggest challenge followed by low literacy rate (27.1%) and trust issues among users (20.3%). This indicates that security, threat and low digital literacy rates are the main barriers for the growth of digital banking.

Figure 14: Biggest challenge in the digital banking growth (pie chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The pie chart suggests the cybersecurity, low literacy rates and trust issues are the major challenges in digital banking services growth.

Table 15: Overall experience of digital banking services (N = 59)

Rating	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	23	39.0%
Good	32	54.2%
Average	3	5.1%
Poor	0	0.0%
Very poor	1	1.7%

Interpretation: Table 15 suggests that the overall experience of the users has been excellent (39.0%) and good (54.2). Only 5.1% gave average experience and 1.7% respondent gave very poor which indicates that digital banking services has been providing the best experience to their consumers overall.

Figure 15: Overall satisfaction with digital banking (pie chart)

Source: Primary Data (Field Survey, 2026)

The pie chart confirms that consumers are having excellent experience while using the digital banking services. Most of users are considering it to be a good experience.

4.7 Hypothesis Testing and Interferential Testing

In this section statistical tool which is used is chi-square test of independence to explore deeper relationship between the variables collected through the primary survey questionnaire. While the previous section of the chapter focuses on the descriptive overview using percentages and frequencies, this section focuses on validating research assumptions through hypothesis testing to determine if key demographic factors actively influence consumer attitudes towards digital banking in India.

4.7.1 Age Group versus Perceived Convenience

To empirically determine whether a consumer's age group has significant influence on how they perceive the convenience of digital banking utilities via a formal Chi-Square test of Independence was done.

- Null Hypothesis (H_0): Consumer age group and the perceived convenience/time saving utility of digital banking are completely independent.
- Alternate Hypothesis (H_1): Consumer age group and the convenience/time saving utility of digital banking are significantly dependent on one another.

Empirical Framework: The cross tabulation table below outlines the exact response distribution across 59 surveyed consumers, mapped against a standard 5-point Likert scale.

Table 4.7.1: Cross-Tabulation of Age Cohorts vs. Convenience Perceptions

Age Demographics	1 (SD)	2 (D)	3 (N)	4 (A)	5 (SA)	Grand Total
Below 18 years	1	0	0	0	0	1
18 - 25 years	0	0	0	2	4	6
26 – 35 years	4	1	1	14	25	45
36 – 50 years	0	0	0	0	4	4
Above 50 years	1	0	0	0	2	3
Grand Total	6	1	1	16	35	59

Note: SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree

Inferential Metrics: The primary calculations derived from the cross-tabulated dataset are represented in the summary table below:

Table 4.7.2: Chi-Square Test Output

Statistical Component	Output Metric
Calculated p -value	0.4690
Significance Level (α)	0.05
Degrees of Freedom (df)	16
Statistical Verdict	Non-Significant Result ($p > \alpha$)
Hypothesis Resolution	Fail to Reject the Null Hypothesis (H_0)

Interpretation and Analytical Discussion: Data processing via the Chi-Square test reveals a final p -value of 0.4690. Processing it against the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ reveals that the output is entirely non-significant as the p -value drastically exceeds our critical value where we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0).

Statistically this proves that there is no significant association or influence of a person’s age with how they perceive the convenience/time saving utilities of digital banking services.

4.8 Qualitative Analysis of Bank Personnel Interviews

A semi structured interview was conducted with the staff and manager of UCO Bank Nakodar to understand the operational efficiency of banks after the introduction of digital banking services, digital banking strategies by banks and adoption by the consumers, challenges they face while using these services etc.

- **Operational Efficiency:** Staff notes that after advent of digital banking services there is noticeable reduction in the routine bank visits of customers for passbook printing, small transactions allowing them to utilize that time to focus on other complex banking services.
- **Digital banking strategies** opted by bank to educate the consumers about the new technologies include special awareness camps organized by the bank for rural and local consumers twice a month, which help the consumers to understand these services very well.
- **Security and Challenges:** The manager (UCO Bank) highlighted that senior citizens still struggle with trust and tech-anxiety, for them cybersecurity remains a primary challenge.
- From branch end it was known that UCO Bank is actively promoting the use of bank's mobile app and digital wallets to match competitor offerings in India as the digital banking is expanding drastically and to match with the evolving trends they (public sector banks) have to keep them update and adapt to new technology as well.

Chapter 5: Findings and Results

This chapter is about the key findings and results collected from the data analysis of the primary and the secondary data observed during the research process.

5.1 National Digital Banking Trends (Secondary Data Findings)

- The analysis of macro level data from the Ministry of Electronics and Informational technology (MeitY) reveals a drastic expansion in the digital banking system across India with BHIM-UPI transaction volumes growing by 62.3% within a single year. This proves that the adoption for digital banking in India has grown to another level specifically with UPI advent.
- This huge growth in the transaction volumes using digital payment methods have ensured that it is not an optional method for consumers now but it is their first priority when it comes to transactions now.

5.2 Demographic Discoveries (Primary Data)

- The dominant respondent demographic lies within the range 26 to 35 age group, representing the working class segment mainly which frequently uses the digital services.

5.3 Digital Banking Usage Patterns

- Good majorities of 86.4% of total respondents strongly agrees or agree that digital banking makes transactions highly convenient and time savings for the users.
- 94.9% respondents (56 out of 59) agree that they use digital banking services.
- 91.5% respondents (54 out of 59) use UPI as their preferred digital banking transaction channel.
- Nearly 64.4% respondents (38 out of 59) use these digital banking services on a daily basis.

- 61% respondents said that poor digital infrastructure and cybersecurity threats are still the major challenges they faced while using the digital banking services.

5.4 Hypothesis Testing Outcomes

- A Chi-Square Test of Independence was executed to analyze the relationship between age groups and the perceived transaction convenience. The test yielded non-significant p -value of 0.4690 ($p > 0.05$).
- Therefore the study failed to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), proving that digital banking convenience is not influenced by the specific age groups and is uniformly recognized by all age demographics.

5.5 Bank Staff Insights

- Qualitative insight from UCO Bank personnel confirms that while digital banking increases internal operational speed, at the user's end still some of the challenges such as cybersecurity fears, lack of digital infrastructure and security concerns remain the biggest hurdles in the complete adoption of digital banking services.

5.6 Major Challenges and Comparison with Observed Trends

- As observed from the primary field survey 61% respondents explicitly identify poor digital infrastructure along with underlying cybersecurity threats as their primary operational challenges. This analysis indicates that unexpected server timeouts, slow OTP generation which leads to transaction delays creates a sense of hesitation among the users.
- 30.5% respondents have experienced technical errors such as server down or glitches that occur while using these digital services also create a sense of dissatisfaction among users.
- Trust and security concerns among the customers also create financial vulnerability. Both the primary survey metrics and qualitative feedback from bank personnel raise the same issue regarding the consumer anxiety due to

phishing risks, security concerns and fake applications and increasing digital frauds.

- The wide adoption metrics recorded in the study i.e. 94.9% and consumer's preference for UPI i.e. 91.5% perfectly align with secondary data and growth patterns reviewed by Reserve bank of India (RBI). This strong alignment proves that the transaction habits of the respondents perfectly reflect the broader nationwide shift towards a cashless economy.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

This chapter comprises of the conclusions made by analyzing the secondary data and the primary data collected from the surveys and the interview with the bank staff. Connecting this research with the core objectives of the project “Impact of Digital Banking in India: Recent Trends and Challenges” and with empirical evidences this conclusion chapter highlights what the research definitely proves regarding the current state of digital banking in India.

6.1 Conclusions based on Objectives:

- The first primary objective of this study was to trace and evaluate the evolution of digital banking in India. From the secondary data analysis there is a sharp shift from traditional banking to the digital banking system in India in the last decade due to demonetization, Covid after effects. Confirming this transition from the empirical studies done on the basis on primary data an overwhelming 94.9% of respondents agreed to adopt the digital banking in some ways.
- The study highlights an evolutionary shift in the payment methods characterized by the absolute dominance of UPI (Unified Payments Interface). From the primary data analysis also it has been collected that 91.5% of the sampled population chose UPI as their primary transactional channel.
- The study verifies that 64.4% of the respondents use digital payment applications on a daily basis which confirms that the impact that digital banking has created on the consumers is remarkable. And the evolution of digital banking in India is no longer an emerging trend but it has officially become the part and parcel of user’s daily life.
- The primary survey demonstrates that the digital banking has made the consumer’s life more convenient and time saving with 86.4% respondents agreeing to this aspect. It has certainly helped in the banking system also by reducing the operational costs by reducing the footfall of the consumers for every small transaction and query at the bank as discussed with the staff and the bank manager in the interview session.
- From the secondary data analysis it has also concluded that with the technological advancements the banking sector is also advancing with the introduction of AI chatbots in the banking apps. The neo banking, fintech advents in the banking sector taking the digital banking initiatives to a whole new level.

- Though there are numerous benefits of the digital banking there are many challenges also which are associated with it. From the secondary and primary data cybersecurity threats, lack of digital infrastructure, lack of digital literacy in rural and semi-rural areas, phishing still makes it difficult for the complete adoption of the digital banking services across India.

6.2 Hypothesis Testing:

- A Chi-Square test was conducted from the data collected in primary survey which checks that is there any direct relationship between the demographic age grouping and the perception of consumers to the convenience and the time saving utilities of digital banking services. The inferential test yielded a non-significant p value of 0.4690 which exceeds the significant level $\alpha = 0.05$, failing the reject the null hypothesis proving that there is no direct relationship or influence of the age group to how the consumers perceive the benefits of using digital banking services.

6.3 Strategic Meaning for the Organization:

- Since the adoption rate for the digital banking services is already very high but to be consistent and for the long term success of the digital banking implementation will depend on converting the hesitant users into high trust and permanent users. This can only be possible by eliminating the challenges faced by the users and the targeted approach followed by the banks for the wide acceptance of the digital banking services even at the rural and semi-rural areas.

Chapter 7: Recommendations / Suggestions

Based on the secondary data gaps from the literature review, the primary survey responses and the qualitative field inputs from the UCO Bank staff and bank manger the following practical recommendations should be considered.

7.1 Actionable Macro Level Solutions

- **Closing the Urban Rural Technology Divide:** As the urban costumers are well acquainted with technology they show the wide user cover of digital banking services in comparison to the rural and semi-rural consumers who lack digital literacy. For that case banks should design the lighter version of their application to run on simple smartphones and the targeted digital literacy camps should also be organized frequently to make rural population aware of the latest digital banking services.
- **Simplifying the User Interface:** Over the years of the evolution of digital banking services it has observed that consumers are reluctant to use the official banking applications more and adapt to quick transactional channels like UPI more. The main reason for that is there are multiples steps to be taken before using the banking applications such as adding the IFSC code, information of the beneficiaries and then a long time for the activation of the accounts. Banks should make their banking applications user friendly by eliminating so many steps so that it can also do the transactions in seconds and result in adoption of these apps also by the users.

7.2 Interactive Technology and Automated Public Education

- **Introducing Interactive Self Service Education Kiosks:** To educate the general public for the digital banking applications and new scheme launches banks should keep large interactive screens in customer lobbies. Customers can use these interactive screens to know about the specific banking apps of that particular bank and their new digital banking launches as well, this will save time for the banking personnel also and for the consumer it becomes easy to get all answers for their doubts without any time constraint and hesitation.

- **Voice Activated AI Assist for Vulnerable Demographic:** To help the vulnerable users (such as a 75 year old customer who struggles to read fine prints and with small app menus), banking apps must integrate voice driven AI chatbots. Instead of typing and searching on the apps the consumer can directly speak with the AI chatbot in his/her local language and get navigations accordingly.

7.3 Managing Multi-App Payment Chaos and Security Threats

- **Promoting Bank-Owned UPI Apps Over Third –Party Platforms:** From primary data inferences almost 91.5% consumers prefer UPI for their digital transactions but the vast majority relies on the foreign third party apps like Google Pay instead of their own bank’s native UPI applications. This is because the banks do not actively promote their own UPI applications. Banks must promote their own UPI applications to the consumers by telling the benefits of using bank owned UPI application as it protects the consumers from their confidential data breach and so reduces the chances of cybersecurity threats and even there is fast resolution of any digital dispute due to the elimination of external middleman app.
- **Centralized Kill Switches for Third Party Apps:** As there is a rapid expansion of the non-banking apps like WhatsApp Payments, Amazon Pay which is directly linked to the consumer’s core banking account. This puts the consumer’s data at risk. Therefore banks should introduce a centralized “**Third Party Consent Manager**” dashboard inside the main app where the user should be able to see every single external application linked to their bank account and have the right or option to revoke permissions or freeze the external access any time they want when they feel that their privacy is compromised or at the risk.
- **Context Aware Safety Pop-ups for External Transactions:** To protect users from phishing links or fraudulent data scraping on social apps, banks must introduce active security features. Any payment transaction originating outside the core bank app (like a payment initiated on WhatsApp or from any other external gateway) should trigger a mandatory, instant security pop-up from the core banking application requiring a biometric scan and a warning line “**You are paying an external merchant outside your bank application. Confirm identity.**” This will catch the immediate attention of the user and he/she will do the payment attentively considering the risks associated with it.

7.4 Improving Local Tech Performance and Trust

- **Fixing Server Capacity during Busy Retail Hours:** To directly solve the 61% digital infrastructure bottleneck cited in the primary data, banks must allocate extra server power during peak operational hours. This will reduce the delayed OTP messages, server timeouts and transactional failure.
- **Accelerated Reversal for Failed Transaction:** The biggest hurdle to absolute consumer trust is the fear of money getting stuck in the system during the network glitch or technical glitch. Banks must ensure the real time reversal mechanism that automatically returns debited money to the customer's account within the time span of 2 hours. This will convert the hesitant users into high trust consumers.

Chapter 8: Limitations

While this research provides the practical insights of the current trends and the challenges faced during the evolution of digital banking in India, there resides some of the limitations also which should be kept in mind while evaluating the final report.

- **Small Primary Sample Size:** The quantitative analysis is heavily reliant on the primary sample size of 59 respondents and the 5 staff members of the bank which is a very small fraction as compared to the millions of active digital banking users. Because of this these results show a small scale regional snapshot rather than a complete national analysis.
- **Geographic Constraints:** As the research was conducted from Punjab, the majority of the responses came from the regions of Punjab and Himachal Pradesh. Even though a few scattered responses were collected from the personal contacts in cities like Bangalore, Jaipur, Noida and parts of Uttarakhand, the sample completely misses the eastern and western belts of India which makes it difficult to generalize the exact findings across the entire country.
- **Strict Academic Time Constraints:** As there were strict time constraints to complete this project which included planning, distribution and analysis, it was not logically possible to track the changes in the customer habits with any new digital service adoption as it needs the close surveillance of at least 1-2 years so the conclusions were made according to the secondary data resources and from the analysis of primary data.
- **Selection Bias:** the questionnaire was sent to the personal and professional network mainly via digitally through smartphone, email and whatsapp, so there are the chances of natural bias. The individuals who responded to the questionnaire were mostly educated and own a smartphone with a stable internet connection.

However the study opens a valuable pathway for the subsequent research. The data is still reliable for the future studies and understanding the topic at the ground level. The recommendations are practical and can be very useful for the policy makers to resolve the challenges faced by the users.

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Appendices

Appendix Questionnaire

Section A - Demographic Information

1. What is your age group?*

- Below 18 years
- 18 to 25 years
- 26 to 35 years
- 36 to 50 years
- Above 50 years

2. What is your occupation?*

- Student
- Salaried Employee
- Business owner
- Homemaker
- Other

3. What is your educational qualification?*

- Below HSC
- 12th Pass
- Graduate
- Post Graduate
- Other

Section B - Digital Banking Usage Pattern

4. Do you use digital banking services?*

- Yes
- No

5. Which digital banking service do you use most frequently?*

- UPI (PhonePe / Google Pay / Paytm)
- Mobile Banking App
- Internet Banking
- Debit / Credit Card
- Digital Wallet

6. How frequently do you use digital banking?*

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Rarely

Section C - Impact of Digital Banking

7. Digital banking has made my financial transactions more convenient and time saving.*

- 1 (Strongly Disagree) | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 (Strongly Agree)

8. Digital banking has reduced my dependency on cash for daily transactions.*

- 1 (Strongly Disagree) | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 (Strongly Agree)

9. Digital banking services are easily accessible and available 24 hours a day.*

- 1 (Strongly Disagree) | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 (Strongly Agree)

10. Digital banking has helped me save money on transaction costs and bank visits.*

- 1 (Strongly Disagree) | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 (Strongly Agree)

Section D - Challenges of Digital Banking

11. Have you ever faced any of the following challenges while using digital banking?*

- Cybersecurity threat or fraud
- Poor internet connectivity
- Technical errors in app or website
- Lack of digital literacy

- Trust and security concerns
- None of the above

12. How satisfied are you with the security of digital banking services?*

- Very Satisfied
- Satisfied
- Neutral
- Dissatisfied
- Very Dissatisfied

Section E - General Opinion & Satisfaction

13. Do you think digital banking has contributed to financial inclusion in India?*

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

14. Which factor do you think is the biggest challenge for digital banking growth in India?*

- Cybersecurity threats
- Lack of internet infrastructure
- Low digital literacy
- Trust issues among users
- Regulatory challenges

15. Overall how would you rate your digital banking experience?*

- Excellent
- Good
- Average
- Poor
- Very Poor

Executive Summary

This dissertation evaluates the operational realities, evolving consumer perception towards the Indian digital payment ecosystems, digital banking trends and challenges under the title “Impact of Digital Banking in India: Recent Trends and Challenges”. The primary objectives of this study were to analyze the current trends and adoption of digital banking services, evaluate technical challenges faced by users and providing recommendations based on the critical analysis of the data collected during the research process.

Utilizing the descriptive research design, the primary empirical data was gathered through a structured questionnaire with 59 responses and a semi structured interview conducted with the staff and bank manager of UCO Bank Nakodar (Punjab) supplemented by the secondary data from various research papers and RBI reports, NITI Aayog reports etc.

In finding it is revealed that while the UPI i.e. Unified Payments Interface has widely dominated the digital banking transactions for daily small payments, consumers use bank owned applications for bigger transactions because of the security concerns.

Furthermost many challenges were also observed during the research like cybersecurity threats, gaps in digital literacy in rural and urban consumers, server timeout and technical glitches still create hurdles in the seamless adoption of digital banking services across India.

The study concludes that bridging these operational gaps need targeted approach from banks and time to time awareness programs for rural population.